

An efficient method for the preparation of hydroxamic acids

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Abstract : Reactions of acyl chlorides with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and NaHCO₃ generate the corresponding hydroxamic acid products in ethyl acetate and water at room temperature for 5 min. This is a simple and efficient method to synthesize a wide range of hydroxamic acids from carboxylic acids in excellent yield and high purity after simple post-treatment without chromatographic purification. In this process, the highlights are the simple separation of products and cheaply available reagents.

Keywords : Hydroxamic acids, carboxylic acids, acyl chlorides, hydroxylamine hydrochloride.

Introduction

The wealth of hydroxamic acids in a variety of metalloproteinase inhibitors has provided a driving force for chemists and biologists to develop increasingly efficient and facile methods toward their preparation because of their strong chelating properties with various metal ions¹. Hydroxamic acid derivatives play a crucial role in the development of new pharmaceuticals such as anti-inflammatory agent, antiasthmatic, antibiotic, psychotropic drugs, insecticide, acaricide and nematocide². As their potential nucleophilicity³ and coordination phenomenon¹, hydroxamic acids have been extensively used in the study of Lossen rearrangements⁴ and nitrogen-containing heterocycles synthesis⁵. Their great importance in chemistry and biology has stimulated the development of efficient methods for their synthesis. Several methods are available for the synthesis of hydroxamic acids⁶. While the common methods for the preparation of hydroxamic acid molecules required harsh conditions, which not only utilize relatively expensive reagents, some of which are commercially unavailable, but also suffer from tedious purification and deprotection which are often incompatible with multiple parallel synthesis⁷.

To address this drawback, we have recently focused on exploiting an efficient method for the synthesis of hydroxamic acids, which allowed the use of easily accessible starting materials and mild reaction conditions. Here,

we described the synthesis of a series of hydroxamic acid compounds from carboxylic acids that provided the products in excellent yield and high purity without chromatographic purification or crystallization.

At the beginning of our study, benzoyl chloride (2a) was used as a test substrate to find the best reactant ratio for *N*-hydroxybenzamide (3a) synthesis, using hydroxylamine hydrochloride and NaHCO₃ in ethyl acetate and water at room temperature for 5 min to achieve the transformation (Table 1). The best result can be achieved in

Table 1. Optimization of the reactant ratio^a

Entry	2a (eq)	NH ₂ OH·HCl (eq)	NaHCO ₃ (eq)	Solvent (EtOAc/H ₂ O)	Yield (%)
1	1	1.0	1.0	2 : 1	45
2	1	1.2	1.2	2 : 1	45
3	1	1.2	1.5	2 : 1	56
4	1	1.2	2.0	2 : 1	95
5	1	1.2	2.4	2 : 1	99
6	1	1.0	2.0	2 : 1	90
7	1	1.2	2.4	1 : 1	85
8	1	1.2	2.4	1 : 0	0
9	1	1.2	2.4	0 : 1	30

^aReactions conditions : All reactions were carried out at room temperature for 5 min.

99% yield under conditions involving benzoyl chloride (1 equiv) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (1.2 equiv) and NaHCO_3 (2.4 equiv) in $\text{EtOAc}/\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (2 : 1) (entry 5, Table 1). The isolated yield of **3a** is merely 45% when the reaction is performed under the ratio of 1 : 1 for hydroxylamine hydrochloride to NaHCO_3 (entry 1, Table 1). The ratio of ethyl acetate and water is also an important factor affecting the yield of *N*-hydroxybenzamide (**3a**). The yield of **3a** is dramatically reduced (30%) in aqueous solution (entry 9, Table 1) and no target product was obtained with ethyl acetate as the solvent.

Under the optimized reaction conditions, hydroxamic acids (**3a-t**) were obtained from carboxylic acids (**1a-t**) in excellent yield and high purity (Table 2). Acyl chlorides were synthesized from carboxylic acids according to the reference⁸. The synthetic route was shown in Table 2. To our delight, a wide range substituted groups all gave the desired products in excellent yield, which included methyl, methoxyl, nitryl, piperonyl, naphthyl, iodo, bromo and chloro groups. Further investigations demonstrated that the yields were hardly affected by the steric hindrance of the substitutes on the benzene rings, the substrates **1g**, **1i** and **1j** reacted to form the products **3g**, **3i** and **3j** in 99%, 93% and 95%, respectively (Table 2, entries 7, 9 and 10). Moreover, indole species such as 1-methyl-1*H*-indole-3-carboxylic acid also gave the corresponding product in 92% yield (Table 2, entry 17).

Table-2 (contd.)

Entry	Starting material	Product	Yield (%)
5	1e	95	
6	1f	98	
7	1g	99	
8	1h	98	
9	1i	93	
10	1j	95	
11	1k	95	
12	1l	93	
13	1m	99	
14	1n	95	
15	1o	93	
16	1p	94	
17	1q	92	
18	1r	99	

Table 2. Synthesis of hydroxamic acids from carboxylic acids^a

Entry	Starting material	Product	Yield (%)
1	1a	99	
2	1b	99	
3	1c	98	
4	1d	99	

Table-2 (contd.)

^aReaction conditions : **1** (5 mmol), **2** (5 mmol), NH₂OH.HCl (6 mmol), NaHCO₃ (12 mmol), EtOAc/H₂O = 10 : 5 ml, room temperature, 5 min, in an open round bottomed flask.

Experimental

Typical procedure for the preparation of hydroxamic acids (3a-t) :

Acyl chlorides were synthesized from carboxylic acids according to the reference⁸. Carboxylic acids (5 mmol) and SOCl₂ (8~10 ml) were added to the 50 ml round bottomed flask, refluxed at 60~80 °C for 5~6 h with stirring. The residual SOCl₂ was removed *in vacuo* to afford the acid chlorides.

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride 0.42 g (6 mmol) was added to a solution of 10 ml EtOAc and 5 ml H₂O containing NaHCO₃ 1.008 g (12 mmol). The mixture was dissolved with stirring at room temperature and an acyl chloride (5 mmol) which was diluted with small amounts of EtOAc was added dropwise. After stirring for 5 min at room temperature, the organic layer was separated from the aqueous layer, dried with Na₂SO₄, filtered, and the solvent was removed *in vacuo* to afford pure product.

N-Hydroxybenzamide (3a) :

White solid, m.p. 123–124 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.85 (1H, brs), 8.68 (1H, brs), 7.85–7.84 (2H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.53–7.51 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.48–7.44 (2H, m); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3298, 3060, 3027, 2754, 1646, 1613, 1571, 1455, 1435, 900, 794, 691; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₈NO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 138.0555; found : 138.0551.

N-Hydroxy-1,3-dihydroisobenzofuran-5-carboxamide (3b) :

White solid, m.p. 165–167 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.07 (1H, s), 8.96 (1H, s), 7.36–7.33 (1H, m), 7.28–7.27 (1H, d, *J* 2.0 Hz), 6.98–6.96 (1H, d,

J 8.0 Hz), 6.08 (2H, s); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 163.6, 149.6, 147.3, 126.6, 121.7, 108.0, 106.9, 101.6; IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3437, 3271, 3070, 3009, 2892, 2249, 2123, 1662, 1057, 1029, 823, 761, 623; HRMS calcd. for C₈H₈NO₄ [M+H]⁺ : 182.0453; found : 182.0458.

N-Hydroxy-2-methylbenzamide (3c) :

White solid, m.p. 116–118 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.36 (1H, brs), 8.57 (1H, brs), 7.36–7.32 (2H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.26–7.19 (2H, m), 2.39 (3H, s); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3223, 3048, 2880, 1618, 1593, 1449, 1165, 1030, 903, 787, 661; HRMS calcd. for C₈H₁₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 152.0712; found : 152.0716.

3-Fluoro-*N*-hydroxybenzamide (3d) :

White solid, m.p. 136–138 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 11.49 (1H, s), 8.66 (1H, s), 7.82–7.78 (1H, m), 7.59–7.53 (1H, m), 7.33–7.29 (1H, m), 7.25–7.20 (1H, q); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3381, 3110, 2856, 1645, 1615, 1477, 1451, 1099, 755, 652; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇FNO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 156.0461; found : 156.0466.

N-Hydroxy-3-nitrobenzamide (3e) :

White solid, m.p. 132–134 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.62 (1H, s), 9.33 (1H, s), 9.33 (1H, s), 8.39–8.37 (1H, m), 8.22–8.20 (1H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.80–7.76 (1H, t, *J* 8.0 Hz); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3434, 3268, 3070, 3007, 2968, 2249, 2122, 1672, 1530, 1352, 1059, 1030, 822, 759, 621; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇N₂O₄ [M+H]⁺ : 183.0406; found : 183.0402.

N-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzamide (3f) :

White solid, m.p. 130–132 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.15 (1H, brs), 8.97 (1H, brs), 7.66–7.64 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 7.26–7.24 (2H, d, *J* 8.0 Hz), 2.33 (3H, s); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3435, 3070, 2250, 2124, 1660, 1055, 1028, 1007, 823, 761, 624; HRMS calcd. for C₈H₁₃N₂O₂ [M+NH₄]⁺ : 169.0972; found : 169.0976.

N-Hydroxy-2-methoxybenzamide (3g) :

White solid, m.p. 121–123 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 10.35 (1H, brs), 9.06 (1H, brs), 8.20–8.17 (1H, q), 7.49–7.45 (1H, m), 7.11–7.07 (1H, m), 6.99–6.97 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 3.98 (3H, s); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3319, 3151, 2844, 2253, 1646, 1481, 1240, 1021, 908, 733, 649; HRMS calcd. for C₈H₁₀NO₃ [M+H]⁺ : 168.0661; found : 168.0665.

***N*-Hydroxy-3-methylbenzamide (3h) :**

White solid, m.p. 112–114 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.75 (1H, brs), 8.33 (1H, brs), 7.65–7.60 (2H, m), 7.35–7.33 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz), 2.36 (3H, s); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3173, 2863, 2354, 1634, 1582, 1030, 812, 740, 690; HRMS calcd. for C₈H₁₃N₂O₂ [M+NH₄]⁺ : 169.0972; found : 169.0976.

***N*-Hydroxy-3,4-dimethoxybenzamide (3i) :**

White solid, m.p. 181–183 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.72 (1H, brs), 8.34 (1H, brs), 7.46–7.43 (2H, m), 7.02–6.99 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 3.86 (3H, s), 3.85 (3H, s); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3388, 3259, 2842, 2255, 1725, 1701, 1247, 1026, 766, 633; HRMS calcd. for C₉H₁₂NO₄ [M+H]⁺ : 198.0766; found : 198.0762.

***N*-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzamide (3j) :**

White solid, m.p. 169–171 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.69 (1H, brs), 8.40 (1H, brs), 7.82–7.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 7.00–6.98 (2H, d, *J* 8.8 Hz), 3.85 (3H, s); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3282, 2972, 2764, 1643, 1608, 1252, 1024, 846, 753, 615; HRMS calcd. for C₈H₁₀NO₃ [M+H]⁺ : 168.0661; found : 168.0665.

***4*-Bromo-*N*-hydroxybenzamide (3k) :**

White solid, m.p. 158–160 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.31 (1H, brs), 9.12 (1H, brs), 7.70–7.65 (4H, m); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3478, 3268, 3069, 3008, 2248, 2122, 1666, 1058, 1030, 822, 759, 621; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 215.9660; found : 215.9665.

***2*-Chloro-*N*-hydroxybenzamide (3l) :**

White solid, m.p. 152–153 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.40 (1H, brs), 8.58 (1H, brs), 7.49–7.46 (4H, m); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3231, 2886, 1631, 1533, 1473, 1063, 904, 749, 618; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇ClNO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 172.0165; found : 172.0169.

***N*-Hydroxy-[1,1'-biphenyl]-4-carboxamide (3m) :**

White solid, m.p. 198–200 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.29 (1H, s), 9.07 (1H, s), 7.87–7.85 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.77–7.75 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.73–7.71 (2H, m), 7.51–7.47 (2H, m), 7.42–7.39 (1H, q); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 163.9, 142.7, 139.1, 131.5, 129.0, 128.0, 127.5, 126.8, 126.5; IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3438, 3269, 3070, 3009, 2249, 2122, 1663, 1058,

1029, 822, 760, 622; HRMS calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂NO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 214.0868; found : 214.0863.

***4*-Chloro-*N*-hydroxybenzamide (3n) :**

White solid, m.p. 142–143 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.88 (1H, brs), 8.43 (1H, brs), 7.86–7.84 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.52–7.50 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3276, 2998, 2685, 1643, 1599, 1557, 1484, 1095, 844, 746, 528; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇ClNO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 172.0165; found : 172.0169.

***N*-Hydroxy-4-iodobenzamide (3o) :**

White solid, m.p. 172–174 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.85 (1H, brs), 8.30 (1H, brs), 7.89–7.86 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.63–7.61 (2H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3288, 3006, 2732, 1694, 1644, 1607, 1551, 1250, 839, 738, 685, 525; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇I NO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 263.9521; found : 263.9525.

***2*-Bromo-*N*-hydroxybenzamide (3p) :**

White solid, m.p. 158–160 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, acetone-*d*₆) : δ 10.37 (1H, brs), 8.55 (1H, brs), 7.66–7.64 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.44–7.43 (2H, d, *J* 4.4 Hz), 7.41–7.36 (1H, m); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3221, 3046, 2876, 1624, 1470, 1319, 1168, 1029, 904, 747, 639; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇BrNO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 215.9660; found : 215.9665.

***N*-Hydroxy-1-methyl-1*H*-indole-3-carboxamide (3q) :**

White solid, m.p. 145–147 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 10.52 (1H, brs), 8.74 (1H, brs), 8.09–8.07 (1H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz), 7.85 (1H, s), 7.49–7.47 (1H, d, *J* 8.4 Hz), 7.24–7.19 (1H, m), 7.16–7.12 (1H, m), 3.81 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 163.8, 136.5, 131.1, 126.3, 122.0, 121.0, 120.6, 110.2, 107.2, 32.9; IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3438, 3271, 3071, 3011, 2884, 2249, 2123, 1654, 1058, 822, 760, 623; HRMS calcd. for C₁₀H₁₁N₂O₂ [M+H]⁺ : 191.0815; found : 191.0810.

***N*-Hydroxy-2-iodobenzamide (3r) :**

White solid, m.p. 165–167 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 10.93 (1H, s), 9.21 (1H, s), 7.89–7.87 (1H, q), 7.45–7.41 (1H, m), 7.30–7.28 (1H, q), 7.20–7.15 (1H, m); IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3437, 3070, 3009, 2249, 2123, 1664, 1056, 823, 760, 623; HRMS calcd. for C₇H₇I NO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 263.9521; found : 263.9525.

N-Hydroxy-3-phenoxybenzamide (3s) :

White solid, m.p. 110–112 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.26 (1H, s), 9.06 (1H, s), 7.53–7.51 (1H, d, *J* 7.2 Hz), 7.48–7.40 (3H, m), 7.36 (1H, s), 7.20–7.06 (2H, m), 7.06–7.04 (2H, d, *J* 7.6 Hz); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 163.3, 156.8, 156.1, 134.6, 130.1, 123.8, 121.6, 121.1, 119.0, 116.6; IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3490, 3253, 3068, 3004, 2248, 2122, 1666, 1057, 1030, 822, 759, 621; HRMS calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂NO₃ [M+H]⁺ : 230.0817; found : 230.0813.

N-Hydroxy-1-naphthamide (3t) :

White solid, m.p. 150–154 °C; ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 11.12 (1H, brs), 9.26 (1H, brs), 8.21–8.19 (1H, m), 8.02–7.96 (2H, m), 7.60–7.51 (4H, m); ¹³C NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) : δ 165.7, 133.1, 132.2, 130.1, 130.0, 128.2, 126.7, 126.3, 125.5, 125.2, 124.9; IR (neat, cm⁻¹) : 3433, 2971, 2880, 2250, 2124, 1661, 1054, 1028, 1007, 823, 761, 623; HRMS calcd. for C₁₁H₁₀NO₂ [M+H]⁺ : 188.0712; found : 188.0708.

Conclusion :

In conclusion, we have developed a simple and efficient method for the synthesis of hydroxamic acids from carboxylic acids. Various substitutes were tolerated and proceeded smoothly in excellent yields. Further application work is currently under progress and will be presented in due course.

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